

Occupational Burnout Levels of Workers employed as Regular and Permanent Workers in the Affiliated Institutions of Konya Provincial Directorate of Family and Social Policies

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*International Journal of
Modern Education Studies*

June, 2018
Volume 2, No 1
Pages: 56-63

<http://www.ijonmes.net>
<http://dergipark.gov.tr/ijonmes>

Article Info:

Received : 17.03.2018
Revision 1 : 27.05.2018
Accepted : 30.06.2018

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine the occupational burnout levels of Personnel Employed in Provincial Directorate of Konya Family and Social Policies and its Institutions according to different variables. The sample of the study is the Provincial Directorate of Konya Family and Social Policies and affiliated organizations. Maslach Burnout Inventory was used in the study. As a result of the research; it is observed that burnout sub-levels of Konya Family and Social Provincial Directorate employees was significant in the level of personal achievement according to age status and it is observed the presence of desensitization in gender category. In other categories, no findings were found in the name of burnout.

Keywords: Responsible management education, meaningful learning, sustainability

Citation:

Tükel, Y., Kaplan, T., Sipahi, K., Atılğan, D., & Aktaş, S. (2018). Investigation of occupational burnout levels of personnel employed in provincial directorate of Konya family and social policies and institutions. *International Journal of Modern Education Studies*, 2(1), 56-63.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays it is necessary to communicate and face to face interaction in many professions. It is observed emotional burnout reactions on the people who work face to face interaction intensely (Cordes and others 1997). In particular, burnout is a situation that reveals itself in the feeling of exhaustion felt in physiological and emotional areas as a result of the inability to cope with living stress due to the nature of profession as when working in occupational groups that require intensive communication with people (Antoniou 2000). The notion of burnout has been intensively studied in recent years with regard to different fields of business. It is propelled that burnout is three-dimensional. One of the most accepted theories on burnout is Maslach and Jackson's three-factor burnout model. Maslach and Jackson identify fatigue as emotional burnout syndrome, depersonalization, and lack of personal accomplishment (Maslach and Jackson, 1981).

Burnout emerges as a problem that threatens the working life in terms of both individuals and organizations. The concept which is defined as "job burnout" or "staff burnout" in English is expressed in terms of "burnout- burnout syndrome- occupational burnout" in Turkish. The burnout that can be expressed as "energy exhaustion in spiritual and physical terms in the individual" arises in the organization as a result of the long-term effect of organizational factors, both job-related and organizational factors. Here, it is considered as an important reason why the individual cannot remove the causes of stress with the resources he has. The main factor that distinguishes stressful sources of exhaustion from others is that it is a consequence of the individual's interaction in the working environment (Maslach 2003; Ashforth and Lee 1997; Budak and Sürgevil 2005; Özdemir and others 2003; Singh and others, 1994).

The researches to determine burnout factors shows that interpersonal relationships, motivation, overwork and the success of a person in coping with stress are related to burnout. The internal contradiction in the workplace and the stress from this struggle causes the workers to get exhausted. The researches that emphasize the importance of stress and motivation in burnout suggest that those who have low motivation despite high work stresses are burned out. The overloading of the individual due to his work and the prolonged period of this high stimulation results in emotional exhaustion (Wright and Bonett 1997). Emotional burnout is also related to the success of the employee in coping with stress. Despite the fact that work stress is at the same level, it is known that individuals who fail to cope with stress are more likely experience emotional exhaustion (Verbeke 1996). Burnout causes people to feel helpless, trapped and exhausted. For this reason, burnout represents a much more negative situation than stress (Levinson 1996). Burnout causes very important changes in the structure of the organization. These changes can be summarized as decrease in job participation and job satisfaction, increase in job separation, decrease in performance, decrease in group affiliation, increase in physical and emotional symptoms, increase in health expenditures and collapse of family life

(Golembiewski and others 1998). The reactions are the types that point to exhaustion in the separation of retirement and retirement of experienced employees (Wright and Bonett, 1997).

METHOD

The study has been made with 850 individuals who work at Konya province directorate of family and social policy and the institutions which are connected to directorate, as regular personnels and service workers. From this environment, 560 individuals have been contacted for this study by using easy to access sample method.

In this research, Maslach Inventory of Exhaustion which is developed by Maslach and Jackson(1985) is used. The scale (MTE) that consists 22 clauses at total, evaluates exhaustion in three different subclasses. First subclass which is “emotional exhaustion”, second subclass which is “desensitization” and third subclass which is “personal achievement” , consist 9, 5 and 8 clauses, respectively. By using form of Maslach Inventory of Exhaustion which is translated to Turkish by Ergin(1992), with 5 options, clauses are evaluated with a grading system which has 5 differend grades, 1=Never, 2= Rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Usually, 5=Always (Çam, Ergin 1992).

To solve the subproblems in this study, descriptive statistical methods and techniques are used. While analysing the data which is gathered from the surveys, SPSS (Statistical Packet for Social Studies) 15.00 program is used. Related to subproblems, frequency(f), percentage(%) and arithmetic mean (Mean) are calculated. To find the relation between demographic varinats and exhaustion t-test and one sided variance analysis(F) are calculated. Tukey test is made for the results which have significant and meaningful p value.

RESULTS

Table 1

Comparison between gender and exhaustion level of employees

	Gender	n	Mean	Ss	Sd	t	P
Emotional Exhaustion	Female	277	19,44	6,80	558	-1,330	0,184
	Male	283	20,28	7,98			
Desensitization	Female	277	8,36	2,87	558	-3,801	0,000*
	Male	283	9,39	3,52			
Personal Achievement	Female	277	31,99	4,53	558	0,540	0,589
	Male	283	31,77	5,18			

* $p < 0,05$

According to Table 1, emotional exhaustion level related to gender is observed at most at males with the value of (20.28). Mean of females is (19.44). In the light of the analysis which is made for to find the relation between gender and emotional exhaustion

level of employees, the result is not significant and meaningful [F(558) = 0,184; $p < 0.05$].

Desensitization level is observed in male employees with the value of (9.39), however this level is observed in females with the value of (8.36). In the light of the analysis which is made for to find the relation between gender and desensitization level of employees, the result is significant and meaningful [F(558) = 0,000; $p < 0.05$].

If the personal achievement level is considered, the value of female's (31.99) are slightly higher than males value (31.77). In the light of the analysis which is made for to find the relation between gender and personal achievement level of employees, the result is not significant and meaningful [F(558) = 0,589; $p < 0.05$].

Table 2

The comparison between ages and exhaustion levels of employees

	Age	n	Mean	Ss	Sd	F	P	Tukey
Emotional Exhaustion	A 20-30	162	20,00	7,79	3 556 559	0,377	0,770	
	B 31-40	214	19,91	7,66				
	C 41-50	138	20,01	7,03				
	D 51 and above	46	18,76	6,16				
Desensitization	A 20-30	162	9,05	3,38	3 556 559	1,297	0,274	
	B 31-40	214	8,76	3,22				
	C 41-50	138	9,11	3,23				
	D 51 and above	46	8,13	3,00				
Personal Achievement	A 20-30	162	30,52	4,86	3 556 559	7,577	0,000*	A<B A<C A<D
	B 31-40	214	32,04	5,18				
	C 41-50	138	32,67	4,34				
	D 51 and above	46	33,56	3,69				

* $p < 0.05$

According to Table 2, those results are achieved from the analysis. According to data which is based on age, emotional exhaustion level (20.01) is observed mostly at the employees whose ages are between 41 and 50. Minimum emotional exhaustion age interval is the age of 51 and above with the value of (18.76). When we look at the relation between the emotional exhaustion and ages of employees, difference between emotional exhaustion and ages is not meaningful, in other words the result is not significant [F(3-556) = 0.377; $p < 0.05$].

The highest level of desensitization is in the age interval of 41-50 with the value (9.11). However, minimum level of desensitization is in the age interval of 51 and above with the value (8.13). When we look at the relation between the desensitization and ages of employees, difference between desensitization and ages is not meaningful, in other words the result is not significant [F(3-556) = 1,297; $p < 0.05$].

If personal achievement is considered, the age interval 41-50 has the highest value with (32.67). The group of personal achievement with the lowest level is 20-30 age interval with the value of (30.52). A meaningful relation is observed in the analysis that has been made of between the personal achievement levels and ages of employees [$F(3-556) = 0.000$, $p < 0.05$]. Ages of employees have significant role on the personal achievement levels.

Table 3

The comparison between level of education and exhaustion levels of employees

	Level of Education	n	Mean	Ss	Sd	F	P
Emotional exhaustion	Primary school	75	19,36	7,94		1,363	0,237
	Junior High School	63	20,39	8,11			
	High School	190	19,26	7,81	5		
	Associate Degree	81	19,13	6,41	554		
	Undergraduate	131	20,95	6,79	559		
	Graduate	20	21,75	7,01			
Desensitization	Primary school	75	9,00	3,93		1,898	0,093
	Junior High School	63	9,63	3,32			
	High school	190	8,65	3,16	5		
	Associate Degree	81	8,23	2,90	554		
	Undergraduate	131	9,06	3,07	559		
	Graduate	20	9,75	3,36			
Personal Achievement	Primary School	75	32,60	4,82		0,758	0,580
	Junior High school	63	31,23	5,90			
	High School	190	31,61	5,34	5		
	Associate Degree	81	32,20	4,23	554		
	Undergraduate	131	32,00	3,90	559		
	Graduate	20	31,65	4,90			

According to Table 3, emotional exhaustion considering level of education of employees is mostly observed at junior high school grads with the value (20.39). Associate Degree is the group of the lowest level of emotional exhaustion with the value of (19.13). The result of the analysis that has been made with emotional exhaustion and level of education of employees is not meaningful and significant [$F(3-554) = 0,237$; $p < 0.05$].

In the view of desensitization, group of master students (Graduate) has the highest level of desensitization with the value of (9.75). Pre-undergrads (Associate Degree) is the group with the lowest level of desensitization with the value of 8.23. The result of the analysis that has been made with desensitization levels and education level of employees is not meaningful and significant [$F(3-554) = 0,093$; $p < 0.05$].

If personal achievement is considered, the highest value which is (32.60) is observed in the primary schools grads. Junior high school grads are the group of the lowest level of

personal achievement with the value of (31.23). The result of variance analysis that has been made with personal achievement and education level of employees is not meaningful and significant [$F(3-554) = 0,580; p < 0.05$].

Table 4

Comparison between type of institution of employees and exhaustion level

	Type of Institution	n	Mean	Ss	Sd	t	P
Emotional Exhaustion	Day worker	99	20,84	7,62	558	1,446	0,149
	Boarding worker	461	19,65	7,38			
Desensitization	Day worker	99	8,91	2,77	558	0,119	0,906
	Boarding worker	461	8,87	3,35			
Personal Achievement	Day worker	99	31,60	4,68	558	-0,625	0,532

According to Table 4, emotional exhaustion considering type of institution of employees is mostly observed at day worker's group with the value (20.84). However, the lowest level of emotional exhaustion observed at boarding workers with the value of (19.65). The result of variance analysis that has been made with personal achievement and institution type of employees is not meaningful and significant [$F(558) = 0,149; p < 0.05$].

In the view of desensitization, while group of day workers has the highest level of desensitization with the value of (8.87), boarding workers have the lowest level of desensitization with the value of (8.87). The result of variance analysis that has been made with desensitization and institution type of employees is not meaningful and significant [$F(558) = 0.906; p < 0.05$].

Analysis of personal achievement level shows that the group of boarding workers has the highest value (31.94) and the group of day workers has lowest value (31.60). According to variance analysis that has been made with personal achievement and institution type of employees, relation between type of institution and personal achievements of employees has been found meaningless and not significant.

CONCLUSION

Whether we are aware or not, our most important resource is our labor in order to be able to sustain the continuity of our lives. Every morning we go out to present our workforce to the service of our community. That's why it's very important in our lives. However, the conditions of today's modern life have negative affects on labor force, in other words, human labor. One of the concepts that we use to describe negativities experienced is 'Burnout Syndrome'. Burnout Syndrome consists of three subtitles as Desensitization, Emotional Exhaustion and Personal Achievement. These subcategories describe the situations of the effects or changes that are reflected to the lives of exhausted individuals (Cemaloğlu Dilek ve Şahin 2007).

The aim of this study is to measure the burnout levels of permanent staff and personnel working with service procurement in Konya Family and Social Policies Provincial Directorate and in affiliated organizations. When we look at the results of the study, it is shown that there is a desensitization on the burnout level of the gender difference. This situation can be explained by the difference in the personality structures of men and women and the role they play in social life (Cemaloğlu Dilek and Şahin 2007). Nevertheless, it was observed that there was no effect of gender on the level of personal success and emotional burnout.

When it is looked at the effect of age on burnout level, the level of personal success is meaningful depending on the age, whereas desensitization and emotional exhaustion can not be observed. The age group with the highest personal achievement level is 51 and above. The reason for this arises from that older people are more advantageous in terms of experience, knowledge, maturity, patience and maturity than young people. According to the research done and obtained data, there is no effect with the Burnout Syndrome in terms of education level and the institutions that is worked in.

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